

CARBON-CARBON MATERIALS AND COMPOSITES USING CVD AND CVI PROCESSING (AN OVERVIEW)

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ABSTRACT

Carbon-carbon materials are a generic class of composites much like the graphite/epoxy family of polymer matrix composites. They can be made in a wide variety of forms from 1-dimensional to n-dimensional using unidirectional tows, tapes, or woven cloth. Because of their multi-formity their mechanical properties can be readily tailored. Carbon materials have high strength and stiffness potential as well as high thermal and chemical stability in inert environments. They must be protected with coatings and/or surface sealants when used in an oxidizing environment.

A method of depositing carbon on carbon filaments or carbon preform structures is through chemical vapor deposition (CVD). The CVD process within a porous body or preform is termed chemical vapor infiltration (CVI). The CVD/CVI of carbon from hydrocarbon gas within a substrate is a complex process. Various techniques have been applied to infiltrate various fiber substrates including isothermal CVD/CVI thermal gradient CVD/CVI and differential pressure CVD/CVI. The CVD/CVI process for carbon deposition uses volatile hydrocarbon compounds such as methane, propane, or benzene as precursor gases. Thermal decomposition of any of these gases is achieved on the hot surfaces of a carbon filament substrate, resulting in the deposition of pyrolytic carbon and the emission of volatile by-products.

Several methods have been used to manufacture vapor grown carbon fibers. Fibers are produced and grown in a hot methane and hydrogen atmosphere chamber containing catalysts such as nickel, cobalt, and/or iron-nickel powder. Vapor growth of carbon fibers initiates and emanates from the catalytic powder. A more recent patented process allows for a continuous method for producing vapor-grown carbon fibers. In this process the catalyst particles are either incorporated in the feedstock of, or produced in, a reactor by the decomposition of organometallics.

Chemically vapor deposited or infiltrated oxidation resistant coatings involves the decomposition and reaction of gases in a chamber to deposit protective inorganic coatings into and on carbon-carbon composites. This process involves the diffusion of gases on the surface and into a carbon-carbon composite structure. This decomposition or reaction of the gases produces a solid oxidation resistant material deposited on the pore walls and fibers of the composite structure.

INTRODUCTION

The development of CC materials began in 1958 and was nurtured under the U.S. Air Force space plane program, Dyna-Soar, and NASA's Apollo projects. It was not until the Space Shuttle Program that CC material systems were intensively researched (fig. 1). The criteria that led to the selection of CC composites as a thermal protection system were used based on the following:
(1) maintenance of reproducible strength levels at 1650°C, (2) sufficient stiffness to resist flight

loads and large thermal gradients, (3) low coefficient of thermal expansion to minimize induced thermal stresses, (4) oxidation resistance sufficient to limit strength reduction, (5) tolerance to impact damage, and (6) manufacturing processes within the state of the art.

- TOTAL RSI CERAMIC TILES – 30,759
- REINFORCED CARBON/CARBON (RCC) (44 PANELS/NOSE CAP)
- FELT REUSABLE SURFACE INSULATION (FRSI) 333 m² (3581 ft²)

Figure 1.- Space shuttle thermal protection system materials.

The wide range of properties of carbon materials can be shown when comparing the tensile moduli of commercially manufactured carbon fibers that range from 27.6 GPa (4×10^6 psi) to 690 GPa (100×10^6 psi). In fabrication, the fibers can be used in continuous or discontinuous form. The directionality of the filaments can be varied ranging from unidirectional lay-ups to multidirectional weaves (fig. 2). The fiber volume used constitutes another variable. The higher the volume fraction of a specific high-strength fiber in a matrix, the greater the strength of the composite. The matrix can be formed via two basic approaches: (1) through the carbonization of an organic solid or liquid, such as a resin or pitch, and (2) through the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) of carbon from a hydrocarbon.

Figure 2.- Multi-formity and general properties of carbon-fiber and carbon

The CVD process within a porous body is termed chemical vapor infiltration (CVI). This process involves the diffusion of gases into the body and the decomposition or reaction of the gases in order to produce a solid product that is deposited on the pore walls and fibers. Chemical vapor infiltration is one of the principal densification techniques used in the fabrication of CC composites (ref. 1). It can also be used to chemically modify the carbon matrix and to produce discrete internal coatings on the carbon constituents (refs. 1, 2, and 3).

FIBER REINFORCEMENT

In the fabrication of carbon-carbon composites the reinforcing carbon fibers can be discontinuous or continuous.

Discontinuous Fiber

Fabrication of discontinuous fiber composites uses short carbon fibers (fig. 3) combined with a pyrolytic carbon (CVD) matrix. This approach to CC composites generally does not have true fiber reinforcement as an objective. Rather, discontinuous fiber substrates have been used to: (1) increase fabrication capability of large-scale structures. (2) achieve a more nearly isotropic material. (3) increase the composite interlaminar tensile strength, and (4) along with continuous filament substrates, obtain a stronger composite by providing additional nucleation sites that serve to reduce composite porosity.

Figure 3.- Models of fiber arrangements for four short-fiber fabrication techniques: (a) flocking lay-up; (b) pulp molding; (c) isotropic casting; and (d) spray lay-up (ref. 4).

Continuous Fibers

Continuous filament substrates use either the properties of high-strength filaments or achieve a high degree of preferred orientation on the macro-scale of the matrix. The fabrication complexity involving continuous-filament substrates is determined by two parameters: the directionality of the filaments and the amount of layer interlocking achieved in the substrate. The plies and filament winding of unidirectional tapes can be used to achieve a highly oriented substrate, usually with no interlocking between layers. Woven fabrics are used to form a two-dimensional laminate with no interlocking between layers. Helical filament winding, which is directional, results in continuous, adjacent layer interlocking. Multi-layer locking is achieved through complex weaving patterns or yarn placement resulting in "multidirectional" substrates (fig. 4).

Figure 4.- Interlocking approaches of continuous filament substrates: (a) tape wrapped, shingle; (b) filament wound, helix and (c) multidimensional.

CHEMICAL VAPOR DEPOSITION (CVD/CVI) OF CARBON CARBON COMPOSITES

The deposition of carbon on the filament substructures just discussed is accomplished either by pyrolyzing an organic matrix or through CVD. The CVD of carbon from a hydrocarbon gas within a substrate is a complex process. Various techniques have been applied to infiltrate various fiber substrates including (1) isothermal, (2) thermal gradient (ref. 5), (3) pressure gradient (ref. 6), and (4) pressure pulsation (ref. 7). The first two have been the most extensively used. The isothermal

technique is illustrated in figure 5. The substrate is radiantly heated by an inductively heated susceptor so that the gas and substrate are maintained at a uniform temperature. Infiltration is normally accomplished at 1100°C and at reduced pressures (6 kPa (50 torr)) with the flow rates primarily determined by the substrate surface area. This technique produces a crust on the outer surfaces of the substrate, thus requiring machining and multiple infiltration cycles.

Figure 5.- Isothermal chemical vapor deposition to infiltrate fibrous carbon substrate.

Figure 6.- Thermal gradient chemical vapor deposition.

In the thermal gradient technique (fig. 6), the part to be infiltrated is supported by a mandrel that is inductively heated. Therefore, the hottest portion of the substrate is the inside surface which is in direct contact with the mandrel. The outer surface of the low-density substrate is exposed to a cooler environment and results in a temperature gradient through the substrate thickness. Surface crusting is eliminated because the deposition rate is greater on the heated fibers near the mandrel, whereas the cooler outer fibers receive little or no deposit. Under proper infiltration conditions, the carbon is first deposited on the inside surface and, in a continuous process, progresses radially through the substrate as the densified substrate itself becomes inductively heated. Infiltration is normally accomplished at atmospheric pressure with a mandrel heated to $\approx 1100^{\circ}\text{C}$ (ref. 8).

MANUFACTURE OF VAPOR-GROWN CARBON FIBERS

Initially the manufacture of vapor-grown carbon fibers produced only short, discontinuous lengths. Nevertheless, these short fibers were attractive for applications such as CC brake pads. Since some believe that the vapor-growth process may produce the first low-cost, discontinuous, high-performance, carbon reinforcing fiber, it is not surprising that several companies currently are conducting pilot-scale studies to evaluate its potential.

Although only recently developed as a continuous process for producing high-performance reinforcing fibers, this technique was one of the first used to produce carbon filaments. Hughes and Chambers first detailed the vapor-growth process in an 1889 patent (ref. 9). In this patent they showed that small carbon filaments could be grown in a hot iron crucible under an atmosphere of methane and hydrogen-the vapor-growth process. Vapor growth is a dendritic type of growth from a catalyst particle. As Hughes and Chambers first discovered, metallic particles normally containing iron as the primary constituent, tend to catalyze the growth of thin, partially graphitic fibers, when exposed to a hydrocarbon atmosphere at temperatures of approximately 1000°C . If the carburizing potential of the gas is low, a fraction of the fibers can be grown to macroscopic length, while still retaining the diameter of the catalyst particle. Because the most effective catalyst particles have a diameter of only 15 nm, these initial fibers are extremely thin. However, if the carbon potential of the gas is raised to a sufficient level, pyrocarbon can be deposited on the surface, permitting the filament diameter to increase to that of conventional carbon fibers (approximately $10\ \mu\text{m}$). This step is critical because of the small diameter of the initial filaments makes them a potential carcinogen. Because pyrocarbon deposit with the basal planes parallel to

the fiber surface, the fiber is highly oriented and has a high modulus. Figure 7 shows a schematic of the various stages of this catalyst-induced growth of carbon fibers (ref. 10).

Figure 7.- Schematic showing fiber growth and thickening stages during vapor-growth process.

Tibbetts and his coworkers at General Motors Corporation used this growth technique to produce filaments with lengths up to 30 cm in an atmosphere of methane and hydrogen (ref. 10.) Several metals (including nickel, cobalt, iron-nickel powder, and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$) have been used as catalysts (refs. 10-12). Even though the feed stock (methane and hydrogen) was inexpensive and process temperatures of only 1000°C were used, the batch nature of the process used for early studies made it uneconomical for commercialization.

To overcome the low productivity of the batch process, Koyama and Endo (ref. 13) recently patented a continuous method for producing vapor-grown fibers. In their process, the catalyst particles are either incorporated in the feedstock or produced in the reactor by the decomposition of an organometallic. A simple schematic of this vapor-grown carbon fiber process is shown in figure 8. The catalyst and hydrocarbon feed are introduced at the top of the heated reactor, and short fibers are continuously withdrawn from the bottom. Fiber lengthening and thickening can be continuously controlled by adjusting the carbon potential of the gas within the reactor. The technique, which could be considered fluidized catalytic growth, allows carbon filaments with varying length, diameter, and physical properties to be continuously produced.

Figure 8.- Schematic of continuous process for producing vapor-grown carbon fibers.

CVD/CVI PROTECTIVE COATINGS FOR CARBON CARBON COMPOSITES

The primary reason that coatings are applied to carbon fibers and CC composites is to provide oxidation or erosion protection. Ceramic coatings made by CVD have been shown to substantially retard the oxidation of carbon fibers. Except for limited-life rapid heating and cooling applications, external coatings on CC composites are usually applied as multi-layer systems. The most successful external coating systems use a hard ceramic as the primary oxygen barrier with a glaze or glass that can flow to accommodate thermal mismatch strains and can seal defects in the hard ceramic coating. A coating system of this type prevents oxidation of the CC that is used to provide

reusable thermal protection for the Space Shuttle orbiter vehicles. This general approach is also being employed to develop structural oxidation-protected CC composites for air breathing engine and hypersonic vehicle airframe applications.

PROTECTIVE COATINGS ON CARBON FIBERS

Chemical Vapor Deposition involves the decomposition and reaction of gases in a chamber in order to deposit solid inorganic coatings. Reaction rates and the chemical and physical characteristics of the coatings are controlled by the concentrations of the reactants, temperature, gas flow rate, and total pressure.

The coating of carbon fibers presents the special problem of producing uniformly thin coatings on thousands of individual micron-sized fibers within a yarn. Coatings thicker than several tenths of a micron or coatings that bond fibers together severely reduce the flexibility of the yarn. Winding or weaving such a yarn can result in both coating and fiber damage. Achieving thin uniform coatings by CVD on all of the fibers within a yarn, without bonding the fibers together, requires a uniform temperature across the yarn and a diffusion of the gaseous reactants and products into and out of the yarn. This diffusion must be rapid compared with the rate of the overall chemical reaction (refs. 14, and 15).

Reduced reactant concentrations, a low total pressure, and mechanical vibration of the yarn are methods of limiting reaction rate, enhancing diffusion, and keeping the fibers separated. Lowering the temperature also produces the desired effect of a decrease in the reaction rate relative to the diffusion rate. However, low temperatures may compromise the temperature uniformity across the yarn and can result in porous, poorly adherent coatings. A method to ensure thermal uniformity and to improve the quality of CVD coatings made at low pressures and temperatures is to perform the process in a radio frequency (RF) or microwave-induced plasma (refs. 16 and 17). Plasma-assisted CVD (PACVD) is currently an important technique for the fabrication of thin films in the microelectronics industry and has been applied to the continuous coating of carbon fibers (ref. 18).

Equipment for the continuous CVD coating of carbon fiber yarns is described in the literature (refs. 13 and 14). Figure 9 shows a schematic of a CVD apparatus used for fiber coating. The schematic shows the apparatus for conventional CVD, where an induction-heated graphite susceptor tube is used to heat the yarn. In the PACVD mode, a stable glow discharge is established by RF coupling to the process gas mixture at reduced pressures.

Figure 9.- Schematic showing a conventional CVD fiber coating apparatus.

Figure 10. Fixturing for rapid CVD.

PROTECTIVE COATING ON CARBON CARBON COMPOSITES

External Protection

The coatings and coating methods now being used for external protection of structural CC composites are SiC and Si₃N₄ outer coatings made by CVD. CVD and carbide conversion of the

CC surface, and bond layers formed by the conversion of the CC surface to SiC. Performance issues associated with the current multi-layer external coating systems are coating spallation due to thermal expansion mismatch with the CC, corrosion of the outer coating by the borate glass sealants, moisture sensitivity of borate glasses, and high oxygen permeability of borate glasses. These problems are being addressed by chemically modifying the inner coatings and developing coating arrangements that limit glass formation. Although the high oxygen permeability of borate glasses is a fundamental limitation, optimization of the current external coating approach and the use of coatings on pore and fiber surfaces within the CC should allow hundreds of hours of component performance.

Internal Protection

The CVI method for providing internal oxidation protection is extremely versatile; it can be used to chemically modify the carbon matrix, to coat the internal surfaces, or to completely replace the carbon matrix with another material. This method is limited to nonoxides when carbon is present and is a time-consuming and inefficient process as normally practiced when used to produce a composite matrix. However, recent work has demonstrated that satisfactory densification of fiber preforms can be accomplished in periods of 24 hours or less if the reactive gases are forced through the fibers and a thermal gradient is maintained to create a front of preferred deposition within the composite (refs. 19 to 21). Figure 10 shows the type of forced-flow thermal gradient arrangement currently being used for rapid CVI within deposited chambers at General Atomics.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The applications and ultimate markets for CC materials are continually developing for both military and commercial use. New domestic and foreign suppliers have contributed to the acceptance of this unique and versatile material through the use of improved high-modulus and high-strength carbon fibers, and the development of new rapid processing CVI technologies. The key to many of the new uses of CC is in the development of improved oxidation-resistant systems for atmospheric use at high temperatures or carbon fibers that provide dimensional rigidity and low thermal expansion for structural applications, and of newer matrices.

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